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Thermochemical decomposition of coffee ground residues by TG-MS: a kinetic study

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Abstract

Dynamic pyrolysis tests of coffee grounds residues (CGR) at heating rates in the range from 5 – 100 °C/min and at maximum temperature of 500 °C were carried out using a thermogravimetric analyser coupled to a mass spectrometer (TG-MS), for online evolved gas analysis, to determine kinetic parameters of thermochemical decomposition of CGR and its biopolymer constituents. During the pyrolysis, the maximum decomposition rate of each biomass component increased linearly with the heating rate. The slope increased with the biopolymer reactivity in the following sequence: hemicellulose > cellulose > lignin.

Main gases produced during the pyrolysis of CGR were oxygen containing species derived from parent biopolymers and primary and secondary vapours (250 – 425 °C), primarily H₂O, followed by CO and CO₂. The use of the Beta zeolite had only negligible effect on deoxygenation reactions, however it significantly promoted cracking reactions of pyrolysis vapours increasing the light hydrocarbons (C₁-C₂) formation with the subsequent improvement in the heating value of the pyrolysis gas.

Kinetic parameters for any of the individual biopolymers in CGR were estimated using the model-free isoconversional dynamic methods: Kissinger–Akahira–Sunose (KAS) and

Flynn–Wall–Ozawa (FWO) models. The average value for the apparent activation energy of the individual biopolymers (hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin) in CGR calculated by KAS and FWO methods: were estimated as 214, 241 and 266 kJ/mol, respectively; whilst for the CGR as a whole it was 242 kJ/mol. The two model-free isoconversional dynamic methods have been shown to be useful tools for assessment of biomass pyrolysis kinetic parameters, as they can provide E_a values for use in reactor design models.

Keywords: coffee ground residues; TG-MS; catalytic pyrolysis; cracking; kinetics; isoconversional methods.

1. Introduction

The depletion of fossil fuel reserves and the environmental problems derived from their utilization have made necessary the use of alternative fuels. Biomass is a clean and renewable energy source leading to environmental, technical and economic benefits. Residues from agricultural production and processing industries are readily available in large quantities. Coffee is the second most traded commodity in the world after oil, and one of the most widely consumed beverages in the world [1]. Moreover, the residues derived from its production are steadily increasing in proportion to the coffee consumption growth [1–3]. Coffee silverskin and spent coffee grounds are the main coffee industry residues [4]. The latter is a residue with fine particle size, high humidity (≈ 80 wt%), organic load and acidity, obtained during the treatment of raw coffee powder with hot water or steam for the instant coffee preparation. Therefore, this residue is generated in large amounts, with a worldwide annual generation of 8 million tons [3]. On an average one ton of green coffee generates about 650 kg of spent coffee ground and about 2 kg of wet spent coffee ground are generated per kg of soluble coffee produced [5]. Coffee grounds are disposed as household waste that may be incinerated and/or

moved to landfill [4]. Some alternative applications for coffee ground residues are their utilisation to produce compost [6], deodorizer or adsorbents [7,8], as well as source of renewable energy or for the synthesis of high value-added chemicals [9,10]. In this latter regard, the pyrolysis is a thermochemical conversion process that, depending on the reaction conditions, can be used to transform biomass directly into solid, gaseous or liquid biofuels, being the latter also a promising feedstock for chemicals synthesis [11]. In this respect, a systematic understanding of pyrolysis kinetics is a key factor for the assessment of feasibility, design, and scale-up of such biomass conversion processes for energy applications [12]. Therefore, we believe that the potential utilization of the generated residues for fuels or high value-added chemicals production by means of its pyrolysis results at least an attractive and challenging solution for this residue, whose worldwide production is still increasing. Therefore, the first, but not last step for its utilization on the pyrolysis process would be its kinetics study to understand the complex reaction mechanism of its different biopolymers decomposition to help on the design of an adequate reactor. Therefore, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) is the most commonly used technique to study the solid-phase thermal decomposition reactions [13]. Although it typically operates in a different form in comparison to a real reactor (pyrolyzer, gasifier or combustor), it provides an understanding of thermal degradation processes occurring during the fuel conversion. In addition, as this study is focused on slow pyrolysis conversion of coffee grounds to solid and gaseous products, the conditions in the TGA represented real reactor conditions much more realistically that would be the case for processes deploying high heating rates, such as fast pyrolysis and gasification.

The thermal decomposition of biomass proceeds via a very complex set of competitive and concurrent reactions and thus, the exact mechanism for biomass pyrolysis remains unknown. Each step likely has its own single apparent activation energy, and thus the use

of an average, global apparent activation energy to define the kinetics of such processes could be interpreted as an inadequate simplification at best [14]. Furthermore, the DTG curves from these models may hide the true multi-stage character of pyrolytic reactions under a single peak [15].

During the second half of the 20th century several novel methods for determining Arrhenius parameters based on a single parameter emerged. These so-called “model-free” methods are founded on an isoconversional basis, wherein the degree of conversion, X , for a reaction was assumed to be constant and therefore the reaction rate, k , depended exclusively on the reaction temperature, T . By allowing apparent activation energy (E_a) to be calculated a priori, these approaches eliminate the need to initially hypothesize a form and rate order for the kinetic equation. Hence, isoconversional methods do not require previous knowledge of the reaction mechanism for biomass thermal degradation. Another advantage of such approaches is that the systematic error resulting from the kinetic analysis during the estimation of the Arrhenius parameters is eliminated [16]. Isoconversional models can follow either a differential or an integral approach to the treatment of TGA data. So, they are considered as a helpful solution for truly determining apparent activation energy [13].

During pyrolysis, due to the poor thermal conductivity of biomass, a temperature gradient is normally developed through the biomass sample between the external surface and the internal part. This gradient may be assumed to be proportional to the particle size, and decreases with reducing heating rate to the point that both, the external surface and the internal part of the biomass particles attains same temperature at a certain reaction time when appropriate time is given for heating [17]. Therefore, a defined particle size range was selected in this study to avoid the effect of the particle size on the determination of kinetic parameters under dynamic conditions of different heating rates.

Therefore, the main objectives of this study were, on the one hand to determine the kinetic parameters for the slow pyrolysis of such promising lignocellulosic residue, coffee ground residues, and its individual biopolymer components (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin) employing isoconversional model-free dynamic methods: Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS) and Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO), due to the advantages they offer in determining Arrhenius equation parameters without the need to make choices regarding kinetic models to be used [18]. The peak decomposition rates of biopolymers constituting the CGR and associated temperatures during pyrolysis process were evaluated. On the other hand, the non-condensable gases generated during the non-catalytic and catalytic tests were also monitored with reaction time and temperature by MS.

The obtained data and models provide important basis for design and operation of slow pyrolysis or staged pyrolysis systems using coffee ground residues for production of biochar and biofuels or high value-added chemicals.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

The biomass employed in this study was coffee ground residue (CGR), collected from local canteen at the University, ensuring that one type of beans was used. As the pre-dried CGR still contained ≈ 15 wt% of moisture, the material was air dried for 24 hours at 105 °C in a laboratory oven before further use. To avoid the effect of the particle size on the kinetic parameters determination, the CGR was crushed and sieved to collect particles in the range of 250 – 500 μm .

For the catalytic pyrolysis test, a Beta zeolite (Si/Al =150) in pellet form supplied by CLARIANT was employed. Prior to the catalytic pyrolysis test, the zeolite was crushed and sieved at same particle size as CGR sample.

2.2. Analytical techniques

The proximate analysis was determined according to European standards: moisture content (UNE-EN 14774-1:2010), ash content (UNE-EN 14775:2010), volatile matter (UNE-EN 15148:2010) and fixed carbon (determined by difference). A thermogravimetric analyzer, TGA (Mettler-Toledo TGA/DSC1) equipped with automatic sample handling was employed to assess the volatile matter and the ash contents of the coffee ground residue. This is a well established thermoanalytical technique for thermal degradation studies of solid materials, such as biomass pyrolysis [13].

A quadrupole mass spectrometer, MS (HIDEN Analytical HPR-20) with an electron ionisation source (70 eV) coupled to the TGA was employed for evolved gas analysis during the pyrolysis experiments. The ultimate analysis of feedstock and was carried out in a micro-elemental analyzer (Thermo Scientific) in order to determine content of C, H, N, S and O (by difference). The higher heating value (HHV) of CGR was calculated using the formula developed by Channiwala and Parikh [19]. The relative abundance of individual biopolymers (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin) in CGR was determined by the sulfuric acid hydrolysis method [20].

2.3. Pyrolysis tests

The pyrolysis tests were performed in the same TGA previously mentioned, at atmospheric pressure. The CGR sample (around 15 mg) was deposited in an alumina crucible with a circular base and total volume of 150 μ l. In this work, all the experiments were performed under non-isothermal conditions at 500 $^{\circ}$ C and different heating rates (HR), 5–100 $^{\circ}$ C/min, with a nitrogen flow rate of 100 ml/min.

A zeolite to CGR ratio of 1:1 (g/g) was selected for the catalytic experiment, in which the Beta zeolite layer was deposited over the CGR sample in the crucible.

2.4. Kinetic models

The one-step global model assumes that the devolatilization phenomena proceeds as a single reaction.

where *Volatiles* represents the sum of the gas and bio-oil, and *char* is the remaining unreacted solid. The fundamental rate of transformation from solid-state to volatiles is generally described by the following expression:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = k(T)f(X) \quad (2)$$

where X is the degree of conversion of the fuel, t is the reaction time, $k(T)$ is the reaction rate constant, and $f(X)$ is a function that represents the reaction model.

The degree of conversion, X , is calculated as its relative weight loss as follows:

$$X = \frac{m_0 - m_t}{m_0 - m_f} \quad (3)$$

where m_0 , m_t and m_f represents the initial mass, the mass at time t , and the final residual mass of the sample, respectively.

The reaction rate constant, k , is temperature dependent, and it obeys the fundamental Arrhenius rate expression:

$$k = A \cdot e^{\frac{-E_a}{RT}} \quad (4)$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor (min^{-1}), E_a is the apparent activation energy (kJ/mol), T is the absolute temperature (K) and R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol·K).

Non-isothermal method employs a heating rate (β), normally linear, to raise the temperature. A linear heating program follows:

$$T = T_0 + \beta t \quad (5)$$

$$\beta = \frac{dT}{dt} \quad (6)$$

where T_0 is the starting temperature, β the constant heating rate (K/min), and T the temperature at time t . Then, substituting equations (4) and (6) in equation (2) gives:

$$\frac{dX}{dT} = \frac{A}{\beta} \cdot e^{\frac{-E_a}{RT}} f(X) \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) represents the differential form of the non-isothermal rate law.

Kinetics analysis is conventionally expected to produce a suitable kinetic description of the process in terms of the reaction model and the Arrhenius parameters. These three components, $f(X)$, E_a , and A , are sometimes called the “kinetic triplet”. There are many methods for analysing solid-state kinetic data [21]. These methods can be classified according to the experimental conditions and the mathematical analysis implemented. The mathematical approaches employed can be divided into model-fitting and isoconversional (model-free) methods. However, as discussed in the introduction section, in this work only the isoconversional model-free dynamic methods were used to calculate the kinetic parameters for the CGR pyrolysis, which require a set of experimental tests at different heating rates. These methods are the Kissinger, Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose (KAS) and Flynn-Wall-Ozawa (FWO) methods. The advantages of the model-free analysis are: its simplicity, and the avoidance of errors associated to choices of a kinetic model [18].

2.5. Model-free methods

Kissinger method

This method allows for the kinetic parameters of a solid-state reaction without prior knowledge of the reaction mechanism. Kissinger [22] developed a model-free non-isothermal method where E_a does not need to be calculated for each conversion value in order to evaluate kinetic parameters. The method equation is represented as follows:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\beta}{T_m^2}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{A \cdot R}{E_a}\right) - \frac{E_a}{RT_m} \quad (8)$$

According to Kissinger, in the differential thermogravimetric curve (DTG), the temperature at which the peak weight loss velocity (in %/min) occurs for a given heating rate is determined by both A and E_a . Then, changing the heating rate the peak temperature

will change. Hence, plotting $\text{Ln}(\beta/T_m^2)$ versus $1/T_m$, should give a straight line of slope $-E_a/R$.

Flynn-Wall-Ozawa method (FWO)

The *FWO* method [23,24] is one of the most commonly accepted methods for the computation of kinetic parameters. It allows for the apparent activation energy to be obtained for each degree of conversion from the equation:

$$\text{Ln}(\beta) = \text{Ln}\left(\frac{A_X \cdot E_{aX}}{R \cdot g(X)}\right) - 5.331 - 1.052 \frac{E_{aX}}{R \cdot T_X} \quad (9)$$

where E_{aX} is the apparent activation energy for a fix degree of conversion X , and is calculated from the slope of the straight line obtained by plotting logarithm of heating rates, $\text{Ln}\beta$, versus $1/T_X$, where T_X is the reaction temperature at which this grade of conversion X is reached.

Kissinger-Akahira-Sunose method (KAS)

The *KAS* method [22,25] is an integral isoconversional technique based on the following expression:

$$\text{Ln}\left(\frac{\beta}{T_X^2}\right) = \text{Ln}\left(\frac{A_X \cdot R}{E_{aX} \cdot g(X)}\right) - \frac{E_{aX}}{R \cdot T_X} \quad (10)$$

where E_{aX} is the apparent activation energy for a fix degree of conversion X , and is calculated from the slope of the straight line obtained by plotting $\text{Ln}(\beta/T_X^2)$, versus $1/T_X$, where T_X is the reaction temperature at which this grade of conversion X is reached.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Biomass analysis

Table 1 summarizes the proximate and ultimate analysis, as well as composition in terms of key biopolymers (hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin) of CGR. The pre-dried sample still showed 5 wt% of moisture because this material rapidly adsorbs moisture during transfer and storage. The table also shows that CGR contains more carbon and less oxygen

(and therefore lower O/C ratio ≈ 0.66) than woody biomass and agricultural residues (O/C $\approx 0.8-1.2$) [26]. Such behaviour is attributed to the higher lignin contents in CGR, which reaches 40.6 wt% (whose O/C ratio $\approx 0.4 - 0.5$), while hemicellulose and cellulose account for 36.6 and 10.6 wt%, respectively. This composition is rather similar to that reviewed by Obruca et al. [27] in terms of holocellulose biopolymers but with larger content of lignin. Consequently, the high heating value (HHV) of CGR, 23.4 MJ/kg, is higher than that of most biomass (17-20 MJ/kg) [26]. However, ultimate analysis also showed that CGR contains more nitrogen (2.3 wt%) than other more commonly used lignocellulosic biomass (0.1-1.0 wt%) due to high protein and caffeine content [4].

3.2. CGR thermochemical decomposition (TGA)

Fig. 1 shows both the conversion curves as weight loss in wt% (A), and their first derivative curves with time (DTG) as wt%/min (B) of the thermochemical decomposition of CGR as a function of reaction temperature under nitrogen atmosphere at 500 °C and at five heating rates (HR): 5 – 100 °C/min. The conversion curves at all heating rates indicate that mass loss of CGR mainly occurred at temperatures ranging from 250 to 500 °C. The conversion curves shift to the right with increasing heating rate as can be observed in Fig. 1(A), which implies higher values of initial decomposition temperature (see Table 2). However, this representation of the conversion data makes it difficult to identify the changes in the slope at different temperatures and reaction rates for the thermal decomposition of the three biopolymers contained in CGR. Therefore, the DTG curves, as shown in Fig. 1(B) were derived from the TG data, showing a first large peak with two remarkable shoulders corresponding to the well-established order of biopolymers decomposition: hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin [28–30]. As the figure shows, the peak with the subsequent shoulders can be clearly distinguished for all the heating rates, with the exception of 100 °C/min. Although the identification of the maximum degradation

rate of lignin in biomass is not commonly reported in the literature, as it usually overlaps with the cellulose decomposition peak [13,31,32], in the case of CGR it was possible, due to the large difference in cellulose and lignin contents, ≈ 11 and 42 wt%, respectively. Based on this initial observation it might be suggested that a more efficient staged pyrolysis process of these materials could be carried out to preferentially obtaining products of decomposition of individual biomass constituents separately when heating the material to different temperatures in stages.

On the other hand, it is evident from the results that increasing the heating rate from 5 to 100 °C/min resulted in a progressive rise in the total volatile matter released at 500 °C from 72.2 to 75.1 wt%, respectively as summarized in Table 2. This behaviour agrees with the theory that heating rate has an influence on the secondary reactions of the primary pyrolysis vapours. So, lower heating rates result in longer residence times of volatiles inside biomass particles and the reactor, favouring secondary reactions such as cracking, re-polymerization and re-condensation, which eventually lead to the char formation [13,17,33–35]. This is normally observed when comparing slow pyrolysis with fast/flash pyrolysis according to the product goal for the pyrolysis process; i.e., biochar production (for slow pyrolysis: 0.1-2 °C/s) or bio-oil production for fast (10-200 °C/s) and flash pyrolysis (>1000 °C/s) [36]. However, it is interesting to see this effect even in the heating rate range still corresponding to slow (5-50 °C/min) or at best intermediate (100 °C/min) pyrolysis here studied because it could be used to modulate the reaction to the desired products.

Fig. 2(A) depicts the temperatures of maximum decomposition rate of CGR biopolymers during pyrolysis as a function of the heating rate. Here it can be observed that these peak temperatures logarithmically depend on the heating rate for the three biopolymers; which implies that at low heating rates the mass transfer limitations are more important than at

high heating rates, at which the maximum decomposition rate for the different biopolymers occurs at similar temperatures.

On the other hand, Fig. 2(B) shows that the maximum decomposition rate increased linearly with heating rate for all biopolymers in CGR. In addition, the observed difference in the slope of these lines suggests that the heating rate affected diverse biopolymers differently; thus, the more reactive the material (hemicellulose > cellulose > lignin) the higher the slope. As lignin is the most stable and complex of biopolymers comprising biomass, its amount is assumed to be the main rate limiting factor in the thermochemical decomposition process of CGR.

Fig. 3 shows the TG-MS spectrum of the evolved gas species during the pyrolysis of CGR at 500 °C and 15 °C/min heating rate versus reaction time. This technique is the only one to simultaneously measure in real time the thermal decomposition and the gas product distribution of a very small sample. DTG curve and temperature profile are also plotted to show which gaseous compounds were evolved at each stage of the pyrolysis and at which temperatures. Water is the principal component, and it has two origins. Firstly, the physically adsorbed water, which is desorbed at ≈ 90 °C; and secondly reaction water, produced at 250 – 400 °C, with a maximum production at 314 °C, originated from various dehydration reactions of the original CGR biopolymers and/or dehydration of the primary and secondary pyrolysis vapours from the removal of hydroxyl groups (–OH) overlapping with the main CGR degradation regime [37]. Fig. 4 displays the gases evolution trends at all the heating rates versus the reaction temperature. In this figure are also two water peaks regardless the heating rate, 5 – 50 °C/min; though both peaks merged as a consequence of the fast heating at high heating rate. The other main gases, whose evolution also coincides with CGR decomposition rate profile are CO and CO₂. On the one hand, CO is mostly produced from the removal of carbonyl groups from biopolymers.

While CO₂ is originated from decarboxylation of –COOH and O–Acetyl groups from the original biopolymers, principally the hemicellulose. But also these oxygenates are originated from primary and secondary vapours; generated in the same range of temperatures, with maximum production shifted to a slightly higher temperature 330 °C. These three oxygen containing gases seem to originate from the thermal degradation of the three biopolymers that constitute the CGR (hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin), which is visible on the DTG curve. Moreover, this is also demonstrated by the two small shoulders to the right from the main peak of these evolved gases.

The removal of methoxyl groups (–O–CH₃) from the lignocellulosic structure is associated with the CH₄ production during pyrolysis. CH₄ is released from the biomass structure as a consequence of multi-step reactions, so the removal of methoxyl substituents of the hemicellulose and lignin and the conversion of the alkyl chain of the lignin are attributed to the CH₄ evolution during biomass pyrolysis [38–41]. The release of (C₁–C₂) and H₂ is mainly due to the instability of intermediate condensable species produced during primary degradation. Thus, as temperature increased, the C–C and C–H bonds break to form free radicals, which are recombined into small molecular compounds like light hydrocarbons C₂H₄ and C₂H₆, while H₂ was mainly produced from the breaking of C–H bonds. These species are evolved to a much lower extent, which might be related to the aromatization or the char structure during the secondary pyrolysis [13]. Fig. 4 also shows that the first appearance of the different gaseous species are shifted to lower reaction temperatures as the heating rate was raised.

Fig. 5 displays the evolution with reaction time of the main evolved gases during a very preliminary catalytic pyrolysis test performed at 500 °C and 15 °C/min by placing a Beta zeolite layer over the CGR sample in the TGA crucible for comparison with its non-catalytic performance. In this figure can be appreciated that the progression of the

oxygenated species, H₂O, CO and CO₂, during the catalytic test matched relatively well with that obtained without catalyst at temperatures below 400 °C, from which their production started to be slightly higher, especially CO. This means that the Beta zeolite employed herein shows certain deoxygenation activity for the pyrolysis primary vapors, but not much. However, is in the light hydrocarbons development where most significant differences are observed, reflecting a severe cracking activity of this zeolite over the pyrolysis primary and secondary vapours with temperature peaks around 475 – 500 °C [42]. On the one hand, the production of CH₄ and H₂ deviated from the non-catalytic behaviour above 405 °C, whilst the production of the C₂ hydrocarbons significantly increased from 330 to 500 °C, with peak productions of C₂H₄ and C₂H₆ at 470 and 485 °C, respectively. The utilisation of this type of catalyst would significantly increase the heating value of the gas fraction due to its higher hydrocarbons content.

3.3. *Kinetic analysis*

The TGA experimental data were analyzed in order to obtain the kinetic parameters using three model-free methods. To avoid any influence of the physically bound moisture desorption from CGR sample, the conversion (in wt%) was calculated from the experimental data collected at temperatures between 150 and 500 °C, corresponding to the active pyrolysis stage where hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin decomposition occurs. Figs. S1(A – C) show the plots corresponding to the Kissinger, FWO and KAS models, respectively, used to calculate the kinetic parameters of the dynamic degradation of the biopolymers in CGR according to equations described in Section 2.3. Data in Fig. S1(A) were used to calculate the A and E_a according to the Kissinger method. This method has the disadvantage that these parameters are calculated just from the temperature that corresponds to the highest weight loss rate (DTG_{max}). So, it means that this method should be employed simply for those samples showing a single DTG peak. In the case of CGR,

these parameters would purely correspond to the hemicellulose degradation, which is the most reactive biopolymer in this biomass, in terms of degradation rate as shown in Fig. 2, disregarding the role of the other two biopolymers. However, the FWO and KAS methods calculate the kinetic parameters based on values of conversion from 5 to 90 wt%, with a 5 wt% step as shown in Figs. S1(B – C), which implies that the kinetic parameters for the individual biopolymers that comprise CGR may be estimated. These lines from linear fit at different conversion levels have fairly high linear correlation coefficients, > 0.995 (as summarized in Table S1), suggesting that the values of E_a and A satisfy accuracy requirements. This can be observed in Fig. 6, where the calculated apparent E_a is plotted as a function of the conversion level for FWO and KAS methods in comparison with that constant value obtained with Kissinger method. Here, it can be seen that E_a increases with temperature and conversion level. This is characteristic of processes with different reaction mechanisms. Even when each of the biopolymers that constitutes the CGR (hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin) has its own apparent activation energy, its thermal decomposition proceeds via a very complex set of competitive and concurrent reactions, due to the synergistic effects between its biopolymers. However, an approximate estimation of the E_a of these components can be assessed from the average values of different steps shown in Fig. 6. Thus, hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin would present values of 213, 240 and 265 kJ/mol, respectively according to FWO method; while 215, 242 and 268 kJ/mol, respectively for the KAS method as is summarized in Table S1.

The results show that the values estimated for the decomposition of hemicellulose are very close to those obtained for CGR using the Kissinger method (212 kJ/mol), which is in concordance as this method uses the maximum decomposition rate to calculate the kinetic parameters. When the conversion increases further than 80 wt%, the apparent activation energy increased sharply from 273 kJ/mol to 347 kJ/mol for FWO, and from

276 kJ/mol to 353 kJ/mol for KAS method as shown in Table S1, which could be due to the re-polymerization and re-condensation reactions leading to char formation. Then, taking into account all the steps in the pyrolysis process of the coffee ground residues, the apparent activation energy for the whole process was estimated as 244 and 241 kJ/mol for KAS and FWO methods, respectively. These E_a results are in correspondence with thermostability sequence analysis of these three CGR biopolymer components (hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin) [43]. Therefore, the lignin content would be the main controlling factor in biomass pyrolysis in industrial processes [44]. In this way, these kind of model-free isoconversional dynamic methods have been shown as a very useful tools to assess the kinetic parameters of CGR, as they can provide E_a values to be applied in models for designing reactors for its utilisation as fuel. Furthermore, due to the ability to obtain kinetic parameters for decomposition of individual biopolymers, the data could be used for designing a more efficient staged pyrolysis process allowing preferential recovery of decomposition products of individual biopolymers separately. Such process would enable more efficient production of high-value chemicals from biomass.

Conclusions

In this work, the utilisation of coffee ground residues, a lignocellulosic residue whose worldwide production is continuously increasing, has been explored for its pyrolysis application through the calculation of its kinetics parameters and those for its biopolymers constituents by thermogravimetric analysis. For that purpose, a thermogravimetric analyser coupled to a mass spectrometer (TG-MS) for the online detection of the evolved gases were employed to perform the pyrolysis tests at different heating rates (5 – 100 °C/min) and at maximum temperature of 500 °C. The results show that the heating rate significantly affected the thermal decomposition of coffee ground residues during pyrolysis. The maximum decomposition rate increased linearly with the heating rate; but

also, the more reactive the material (hemicellulose > cellulose > lignin) the higher the slope.

Main gases produced during the pyrolysis of CGR were oxygen containing species, and were evolved between 250 and 425 °C, with H₂O being the most important (from the removal of hydroxyl groups –OH), followed by CO (from decarbonylation reactions) and CO₂ (from decarboxylation reactions) of parent biopolymers and primary and secondary vapours. The use of the Beta zeolite had only negligible effect on deoxygenation reactions, however it significantly promoted cracking reactions of pyrolysis primary and secondary vapours giving rise to a significant increase of light hydrocarbons formation (C₁-C₂) with the subsequent improvement in the heating value of the pyrolysis gas.

Kinetic parameters of the pyrolysis process were determined using isoconversional methods. While with the Kissinger method a single value for the apparent activation energy was obtained (212 kJ/mol), which correspond to the hemicellulose decomposition (as the most reactive component in this biomass), KAS and FWO methods showed that the E_a increases with the conversion level, revealing a complex set of competitive and concurrent reactions. The average value for the E_a of the hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin from these two methods were equal to 214, 241 and 266 kJ/mol, respectively. Whereas the apparent activation energy for the whole pyrolysis process would increase up to 242 kJ/mol. The use of model-free isoconversional dynamic methods proved to be valuable to assess the kinetic parameters of CGR. The E_a values for pyrolysis of CGR are important input parameters for modelling and design of reactors and their optimisation for production of biochar, fuels or high added-value chemicals.

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Table 1. Proximate, ultimate and biopolymers analyses of dry coffee ground residues

Analysis	Coffee ground residues (CGR)
Moisture (wt%)	5.0
Proximate analysis, db (wt%)	
Ash	0.9
Volatile Matter	76.4
Fixed Carbon	22.7
Ultimate analysis, db (wt%)	
C	53.9
H	7.1
N	2.3
O	35.8
HHV (MJ kg _{db} ⁻¹)	23.4
Cellulose	10.6
Hemicellulose	36.6
Lignin	40.6
Others*	12.2

db: dry basis

* Organic extractives unidentified compounds and ash determined by difference

Table 2. Decomposition characteristic of coffee ground residues (CGR) at different heating rates

Heating rate (°C min ⁻¹)	T _i (°C)	T _{DTGmax} (°C)	DTG _{max} (wt% min ⁻¹)	X _{max, 500°C} (wt%)
5	173	300	3.5	72.2
10	180	310	6.9	72.9
15	200	315	10.3	73.6
25	216	321	16.9	73.7
50	225	330	34.6	74.6
100	237	336	68.5	75.1

Figures

Figure Captions

Fig. 1. TG (A) and DTG (B) curves of the thermal decomposition of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C and at different heating rates (5 – 100 °C/min).

Fig. 2. Temperature of maximum DTG (A) and DTG_{max} values (B) corresponding to the peaks associated to the thermochemical decomposition of three biopolymers (hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin) of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C and at different heating rates (5 – 100 °C/min).

Fig. 3. Conversion and DTG curves, and evolved gaseous species (MS signal) versus reaction time during the pyrolysis of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C (heating rate: 15 °C/min).

Fig. 4. Evolution of the gaseous species (MS signal) versus reaction time during the pyrolysis of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C and different heating rates.

Fig. 5. Evolution of the gaseous species (MS signal) versus reaction time during the non-catalytic (red) and catalytic (blue) pyrolysis of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C (heating rate: 15 °C/min).

Fig. 6. Calculated apparent activation energy for pyrolysis of coffee ground residues (CGR) by the Kissinger, FWO and KAS kinetic methods for heating rates of between 5 and 50 °C/min.

Fig. 1. TG (A) and DTG (B) curves of the thermal decomposition of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C and at different heating rates (5 – 100 °C/min).

Fig. 2. Temperature of maximum DTG (A) and DTG_{max} values (B) corresponding to the peaks associated to the thermochemical decomposition of three biopolymers (hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin) of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C and at different heating rates (5 – 100 °C/min).

Fig. 3. Conversion and DTG curves, and evolved gaseous species (MS signal) versus reaction time during the pyrolysis of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N_2 atmosphere at 500 °C (heating rate: 15 °C/min).

Fig. 4. Evolution of the gaseous species (MS signal) versus reaction temperature during the pyrolysis of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C and different heating rates.

Fig. 5. Evolution of the gaseous species (MS signal) versus reaction time during the non-catalytic (red) and catalytic (blue) pyrolysis of coffee ground residues (CGR) under N₂ atmosphere at 500 °C (heating rate: 15 °C/min).

Fig. 6. Calculated apparent activation energy for pyrolysis of coffee ground residues (CGR) by the Kissinger, FWO and KAS kinetic methods for heating rates of between 5 and 50 °C/min.